

KIDWAI : A NEW ROUTE TO SUBSTITUTED-ETHYLENEDIAMINES

TABLE 2-SYNTHESIS AND PHYSICAL DATA OF SUBSTITUTED-ETHYLENEDIAMINES (3)

Compd.	Reflux time h	M.p. °C	Yield %
2-(Benzal)ethylenediamine	20	118	70
2-(<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl)-ethylenediamine	24	125	75
2-(<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl)-ethylenediamine	28	138	74
2-(<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl)-ethylenediamine	24	116	72
2-(Furfuryl)ethylenediamine	20	130	68
2-(Cinnamyl)ethylenediamine	30	140	74
2-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylenediamine	30	110	68

118° (Found : C, 60.88 ; H, 7.80 ; N, 15.76. $C_9H_{14}N_2$ requires : C, 61.0 ; H, 7.90 ; N, 15.8%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 500, 3 350, 3 180, 1 580, 1 465, 1 220 and 740 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 7.38 (b, NH_3^+), 7.21 (m, C_6H_5), 3.53 (s, $ArCH_3$) and 2.2 (m, NH_2).

References

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